

**A Convenient Method for the Preparation
of 4-En-3-one Steroids**

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IN view of synthetic utility of the title compounds and several steps involved in their synthesis¹, we describe here a more convenient and single step synthesis of the said compounds in quantitative yields. This method involves the reaction of pyridinium dichromate² with cholesterol, β -sitosterol and stigmasterol affording cholest-4-en-3-one, stigmast-4-en-3-one and stigmast-4,22-dien-3-one respectively in quantitative yields. The novelty of this reaction lies in its simplicity and one-step clean process.

In this reaction, initially 5-en-3-one an β,γ -unsaturated ketone is formed by the oxidation of hydroxyl group, which due to the presence of pyridine in the reaction mixture, isomerises into more stable, α,β -unsaturated ketone, 4-en-³-one by double bond shifting. Structures of the compounds were supported by their elemental analysis and spectral data.

Experimental

Reaction of cholesterol with pyridinium dichromate. General procedure: To a solution of cholesterol (1.0 g, 2.06 mmol) in dimethylformamide (20 ml) was added pyridinium dichromate (10.30 mmol)

and the reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at room temperature. The mixture was then extracted with ether and the ether extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The crude product obtained after removal of the solvent was purified by column chromatography over silica gel (20 g), elutant : light petroleum/ether, 5 : 1) to give cholest-4-en-3-one (yield 84%).

Under similar reaction conditions β -sitosterol and stigmasterol afforded their respective α,β -unsaturated ketones (yield 73–77%).

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References

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